

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Public Figures

Use Case

Kim Perkins is researching the topic of racial profiling. To this end, Kim Perkins is conducting interviews in German-speaking countries with police officers and politicians who are in charge of local law enforcement. Some of the interviews contain official statements, but they also provide insights into everyday situations in police work and into personal mindsets and interpretations, some of which contradict the official principles.

Kim Perkins has agreed with the police officers that their statements will only be used anonymously and has obtained their informed consent to do so. Kim Perkins is wondering whether the local politicians can be considered public figures and what impact this would have on handling their personal data.

Who is considered a public figure?

There is a difference between «absolute public figures» and «limited public figures.» Absolute public figures are people who have an impact beyond their time, for example, a pope or a US president. Limited public figures are people who have a public role for a certain period of time and then disappear into so-called privacy again, for example, sitting members of parliament, members of a cantonal executive council, or CEOs of a company.

Is it also necessary to protect the privacy of public figures?

In principle, every person's privacy must be protected, and every person can appeal to data-protection laws. Public figures are also entitled to privacy protection with regard to their private lives. However, they must tolerate some infringements of their personality if these infringements relate to their public position. This means that statements they make do not have to be anonymized if they relate to

their public role and if the public interest outweighs the protection of their personality. In contrast to absolute public figures, limited public figures only have to tolerate infringements on their personality in relation to their current public activities. If a limited public figure has disappeared into privacy again—for example, after leaving a public office—they are once again a private person. All the data related to this person must then be treated accordingly, meaning that all personal data may only be published with the informed consent of the person concerned.

Are there cases where informed consent does not need to be obtained?

In principle, informed consent to process data must also be obtained from public figures. One exception is when the data consist in public statements, like a speech at a public event or a television interview. You can use these for research without having to obtain consent.

In exceptional cases, there may also be a preponde-

rant public interest in publishing a public figure's personal data, such as when politicians accept donations or evade taxes. Then you can forego obtaining the public figure's consent. However, you must always carefully deliberate whether the research in question really is a matter of preponderant public interest that clearly outweighs the public figure's interest in protecting their personality. In the event of a legal dispute, the arguments must stand up to judicial scrutiny, so it is recommended to seek the advice of a data-protection officer before publishing the data.

What problems can arise in anonymizing the data of public figures?

In the case of public figures—as in the case of [small groups of study subjects](#)—it is often impossible or difficult to anonymize the data. Even if their name and other personal characteristics are omitted, public figures usually remain identifiable through the name of their office or professional activity.

In individual cases, information that is not relevant to the analysis can be omitted or abstracted. For example, instead of mentioning the name and office of a politician, an interviewee can simply be referred to as a «local politician.» But you must be careful that the reference group is large enough so that the «local politician» cannot be identified based on the small number of such people. When anonymizing the data of public figures, you also have to pay attention to, for example, publicly accessible documents about them. If, for example, a politician who regularly expresses opinions about integration in media appearances is interviewed for research on that topic, their

public statements may make it possible to identify them in the academic publication, even if personal details are omitted.

Researchers must therefore also always transparently inform public figures about the research project in detail, explain how they will use the research data (including with regard to questions of archiving and reusing it), and have them sign an informed-consent document. If necessary, you can also make an agreement with the study subjects that you will let them review quotes from an interview before the quotes are used in a publication.

What does that mean for this case?

Kim Perkins is able to paraphrase the police officers' statements in the publication or to reproduce some of them anonymously. Since the study group is very large, the statements cannot be traced back to individual people.

A police chief has given her personal assessment of the local situation in a confidential interview. Kim Perkins has agreed to let her review the quotes from the interview before they are used in a publication. The police chief does not want some of her statements to be published. Kim Perkins cannot use those ones in her publications, as it is not possible to anonymize the police chief's statements completely.

Local politicians are considered limited public figures. Kim Perkins is not sure whether the public interest outweighs the protection of the local politicians' personalities. For this reason, Kim Perkins will only reproduce their statements if they can be anonymized or if the interviewees have given their consent. Kim Perkins finds public interviews in daily newspapers with similar statements by the politicians that can be quoted.